

Research Paper

Active middle ear implants—Enhanced efficiency of oval window stimulation with larger piston size

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Direct piston-stimulation of the oval window with a middle ear implant, following a stapedotomy or stapedectomy, is one treatment option for patients with otosclerosis. Here, we experimentally investigated whether increasing the surface area of the actuated piston enhances transmission efficiency in oval window (OW) stimulation.

Methods: Fresh-frozen human cadaveric temporal bones (N = 14) were used to evaluate the output of different oval window couplers (OWCs) of A = 0.38 mm², 1.26 mm², 3.06 mm² by intracochlear pressure difference measurements between scala vestibuli (P_{SV}) and scala tympani (P_{ST}). Following stapedectomy, a piezoelectric transducer was used for OWC actuation. Additionally, a numerical model was also developed to estimate the output of the floating mass transducer (FMT, MEDEL, Austria).

Results: Across frequencies, the average pressure difference was 18 and 8 dB higher for the large and medium OWC compared to the small OWC, respectively. Statistical analyses showed significant differences (p < 0.05) between piston diameters across most frequencies. Numerical simulation results using the volume displacement at the OW showed smaller output differences from 0.3 to 10 kHz, indicating that leakage at open gaps after stapedectomy has to be taken into account.

Conclusion: Our findings confirm that, for active stimulation with an actuator, increasing the surface area of the OWC enhances output efficiency proportionally. Nevertheless, volume leakage at open gaps to the OW may contribute additionally.

1. Introduction

Active middle ear implants (AMEIs) such as the Vibrant Soundbridge (VSB, MED-EL Medical Electronics, Austria) coupled to the ossicular chain are a viable treatment option for patients with moderate to severe sensorineural hearing loss (Lenarz et al., 1998). Alternative coupling modalities of the VSB (Busch et al., 2016) allow for coupling the floating mass transducer (FMT, MED-EL, Austria) of the VSB to the oval window (OW) or round window (RW) in order to overcome mixed hearing loss (MHL). Implantation of the VSB, which is currently the only commercially available AMEI, can be adapted to the patient-specific needs and anatomical conditions of the middle ear: in absence of a stapes

superstructure, the piston-shaped oval window coupler (OWC, MEDEL, Austria) can be directly placed onto the stapes footplate (SFP) (Hüttenbrink et al., 2010), hence preserving the physiological hearing sound transmission direction to the OW (forward stimulation). The flexibility in coupling the FMT to different parts of the middle ear or the cochlea also allows for the combination of a stapedotomy procedure using a passive piston prosthesis and the FMT attached to the incus at the same time, known as Power-Stapes (Kontorinis et al., 2011). Additionally, Schwab et al. demonstrated that the OWC with the FMT can be successfully used to stimulate the perilymph through a perforation of the OW (Schwab et al., 2012). One factor potentially affecting audiological outcomes of VSB implantations following OW stimulation, (also known

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as direct acoustic cochlear stimulation) is the diameter/surface area of the piston in the perilymphatic space. Unfortunately, results of preceding studies on piston size in reconstructive middle ear surgeries and active piston stimulation are controversial. A recent clinical study on implantations with an AMEI designed for direct acoustic cochlear stimulation demonstrated that a decreased effective surface area of the piston reduces stimulation efficiency by approx. 30 dB, as expected from the area ratio between the piston and the SFP (Busch et al., 2021). In contrast thereto, the majority of studies investigating clinical results of stapesplasties where a piston prosthesis is guided through a perforation of an ossified SFP and driven by the ossicles (Shea, 1962) found no significant differences in favor of using passive prostheses with a larger piston diameters in their patient cohorts (Cavaliere et al., 2012; Fucci et al., 1998; Hornung et al., 2011). Nevertheless, a lumped element model developed by Rosowski et al. (Rosowski and Merchant, 1995) showed a clear gain when using larger piston diameters. This was confirmed by other clinical studies of Laske et al. and Blijleven et al., who found better air-bone-gap (ABG) closure using piston prostheses of 0.6 mm diameter instead of 0.4 mm (Blijleven et al., 2024; Laske et al., 2011). However, these studies focus onto reconstructive middle ear surgery using passive piston prostheses, and results hence differ from the scenario where an AMEI attached to a piston prosthesis directly stimulates the cochlea. Results for the multitude of studies conducted in middle ear reconstruction using passive prostheses don't come to an ultimate clear answer if piston size matters (Wegner et al., 2016).

Within the present study, cadaver experiments were conducted in a controlled environment to create further evidence on the effect of the piston diameter onto the output efficiency when treating hearing loss with an AMEI for direct acoustic stimulation of the cochlea.

2. Methods

2.1. Temporal bone preparation & reference measurements

The ethics committee of the Hannover Medical School approved the use of TBs, which were obtained anonymously. (10471_BO_K_2021). In total, 14 fresh-frozen human temporal bones (TBs) were used for the present study. All specimens were stored in a freezer at $-21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and kept at room temperature to be defrosted on the day of the experiment. A posterior tympanotomy with removal of the facial nerve provided a wide access to the middle ear, round and OW. A clamp attached to a magnetic stand fixed the TBs during the experiments (Grossöhmichen et al., 2017).

Initially, acoustic stimulation was conducted using a loudspeaker (DT48, Beyerdynamic, Germany) attached to a sound applicator cemented into the external auditory canal to test the state of the middle ear in each TB. Sound pressure level was measured with a probe microphone (ER-7C, Etymotic Research Inc., USA) 1–2 mm in front of the tympanic membrane. The middle ear transfer function (METF) of all TBs was checked with a laser-Doppler vibrometer (LDV) system (Polytec CLV700, HLV1000, Waldborn, Germany) according to the ASTM standard (ASTM, 2005): acoustic stimulation was applied to the external auditory canal and the stapes crus displacement response was recorded using LDV. The laser head was mounted on a surgical microscope (OPMI 1, Zeiss, Germany). A small piece of reflective tape ($\approx 1 \times 1\text{ mm}$) was used to increase the reflected signal at the measurement site.

After determination of the METF, cochleostomies were performed using a diamond drill ($\phi = 0.4\text{ mm}$, Karl Storz, Germany), which allowed for sequential insertion of optical pressure sensors (FISO Technologies, FOP-M260, Veloce 50) into scala vestibuli (SV) and scala tympani (ST) to measure intracochlear pressures in response to the acoustic stimulation (Fig. 1A). The pressure sensors (FISO Technologies, FOP-M260, Veloce 50; see (Grossöhmichen et al., 2017) for details) were calibrated prior to the experiments. During insertion, the middle ear cavity was filled with saline to avoid air bubbles entering the cochlea. The pressure probes were sealed and fixed after insertion with cyanoacrylate glue (Sekundenkleber, UHU, Germany). After fixation of the probes to the promontory, pressure measurements in response to acoustic stimulation were performed to quantify the intracochlear pressure difference (ICPD) generated by the acoustic sound pressure P_{OEC} measured at the tympanic membrane. The pressure difference (P_{diff}^A) was calculated as the vector difference between the sound pressures in SV (P_{sv}) and ST (P_{st}) and the acoustic transfer function P_{diff}^A/P_{OEC} was used as reference for later determination of the equivalent sound pressure level. Subsequently, ICPD measurements were repeated in response to stimulation by the electromechanical devices, and the corresponding electromechanical transfer function (P_{diff}^{EM}/U_{in}) was calculated based on the input voltage U_{in} applied to the device in experiments (Grossöhmichen et al., 2017).

Finally, the equivalent sound pressure level L_E (Eq. (1) in eq. dB SPL for any other (maximum) input voltage E_{max} is calculated as:

$$L_E = 20 \log_{10} \left[\frac{P_{diff}^{EM} \cdot P_{OEC}}{P_{diff}^A \cdot U_{in}} E_{max} / (2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}) \right] \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. The intracochlear pressure measurement setup. (A) The measurement setup for the acoustic stimulation through the external auditory canal. Intracochlear pressure measurement setup for the oval window stimulation using (B) the FMT and the (C) piezo electric actuator for stimulation.

After performing the acoustic reference measurements, the sound applicator was taken out of the external ear canal and the ossicles and tympanic membrane were sequentially removed.

2.2. Exp. 1 – OW stimulation with the FMT

In the first set of experiments (N=8 out of 14 TBs, TB03-TB12), the SFP was removed (stapedectomy) to electromechanically stimulate the cochlear perilymph using the FMT of the VSB through the OW. The FMT was attached to the commercially available oval window coupler (OWC, surface area of $A=0.38 \text{ mm}^2$; MED-EL, Austria, Fig. 2A, B), which will be referred to as “oval window coupler small” (OWC-S) in the following. The FMT was positioned within the middle ear cavity such that the tip of the OWC-S was inserted through the OW about 1 mm into the perilymph at the SV (Fig. 1B). Subsequently, FMT stimulation was conducted, and the intracochlear pressure as well as the FMT vibration at the front side of the OWC were recorded. The FMT was held in place with a stiff wire ($\phi = 1 \text{ mm}$) glued to the cable of the FMT.

The measurements were repeated using the same FMT with the coupler attached to two different silicone shoe adapters with different surface areas (medium: OWC-M, $A=1.26 \text{ mm}^2$; large: OWC-L, $A=3.06 \text{ mm}^2$; see Fig. 2A). The silicone shoe adapters had been designed to be inserted into the OW with a depth of less than 1 mm (Gil Mun et al., 2019), utilizing a sealing ring marker specifically intended for this purpose. The average size of the oval window has been reported to range between 2.8 mm^2 and 3.2 mm^2 (Zdilla et al., 2018). As shown in Fig. 2A, the relative area difference between the circular OWC-S and the oval window rim, referred to here as the “open gap,” is the largest. In contrast there is approximately no open gap for the elliptic OWC-L. Assuming 3.2 mm^2 as the maximum oval window size, the surface open gap ratios (Fig. 2C) for OWC-S, OWC-M, and OWC-L were approximately 88 %, 38 %, and 4 %, respectively.

Finally, the intracochlear pressure differences in response to the FMT

stimulation were measured and recorded to calculate the output equivalent sound pressure level (eq. SPL; (Grossöhminen et al., 2017)). In the first experiment using the FMT, the intracochlear pressure was not recordable with sufficient signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in all measurements, specifically at small piston sizes. Therefore, we decided to employ a piezoelectric actuator with higher force and displacement output in order to measure the intracochlear pressure data with sufficient SNR in a separate second set of experiments using new temporal bone specimens.

2.3. Exp. 2 –OW stimulation with a piezoelectric actuator

Due to insufficient SNR levels with FMT stimulation, a second set of experiments was conducted in 6 TBs (TB17-TB27). The FMT was replaced by a piezoelectric actuator (P842k168, Physik Instrumente, Karlsruhe, Germany) driven by a power piezo amplifier (E618-10 G, Physik Instrumente, Germany) (Fig. 2E). The use of this actuator instead of the FMT also prevents the potential mechanical influence of the spring element created by the sealing silicone ring around the developed OWC-M and OWC-L by overcoming output force limitations. In contrast to experiment 1, the size of the actuator required removal of the posterior part of the ear canal to create sufficient space for placing the piezoelectric actuator into the OW (Fig. 1C).

A custom-made titanium adapter with a round tip of equal diameter to the FMT was attached to the piezoelectric actuator (Fig. 2E, F), allowing for the same experimental procedure as in the first set of experiments: firstly, the OWC alone (OWC-S) was attached to the adapter tip and used to directly stimulate the perilymph after stapedectomy. Secondly, the procedure was repeated with both, the medium (OWC-M) and larger (OWC-L) silicon adapter attached to the OWC. Placement of the stimulator into the center of the OW was facilitated using a micro-manipulator (M3301R, World Precision Instruments Germany GmbH, Germany). For each experiment, piezo actuator stimulation was

Fig. 2. Stimulation devices and the developed accessories. (A) Oval window coupler without additional silicone adapter (OWC-S), (B) top to bottom: medium (OWC-M) and large (OWC-L) size silicone shoe adapters. The piston part of the OWC-S is circular and the designed silicone adapters have an elliptic cross section. (C) 3D sketch of FMT attached to the OWC-M inserted into an elliptical volume (blue) representing the OW and the cochlear perilymph to illustrate the open gap i.e. the area difference between oval window (stapes footplate) and the attached OWC-M. (D) Photo of the FMT attached to the OWC-M. (E) The piezoelectric actuator attached to the titanium adapter that can be coupled to the OWC (F) and the silicone shoes (zoomed-in). The ring of the silicone adapter and the effective area of the OWC-L are illustrated (red).

conducted, and the intracochlear pressure (P_{SV} , P_{ST}) to determine the equivalent sound pressure level (eq. SPL) as well as the vibration at the front side of the OWC (measured by LDV) were recorded.

2.4. Data acquisition and acoustic stimulation

Measurements were conducted in stepped-sine mode using a configurable data acquisition device (cDAQ-9189, NI-9234, Austin TX, National Instruments, USA) with 24-bit resolution analog output (NI-9260) and input (NI-9234) modules. The synthesized stimulation signal consisted of 23 logarithmically spaced sine waves from 0.1 to 10 kHz. The data were sampled at 25.6 kS/s and averaged 50 to 1000 times to obtain a SNR of at least 6 dB. A buffer amplifier (SA1, TDT, USA) was connected between the signal generator and the loudspeaker to provide the required power.

2.5. Lumped element model

As mentioned above, valid experimental results with the FMT were sparse due to low intracochlear pressure with insufficient SNR especially with small pistons. Therefore, we developed a lumped element model of the FMT coupled with an OWC to the cochlea based on previously reported models (Böhnke et al., 2013; Heckeler and Eiber, 2017) to estimate the output of the FMT in such cases. A detailed model description is provided in the supplementary information file.

2.6. Statistics

One way repeated measure of ANOVA on ranks ($p < 0.05$; Sigmaplot, Version 14.0) was used to test output level differences for piezoelectric actuator stimulation with different piston surface areas. Normal distribution of single frequency data and averaged across frequency bands was tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test (Sigmaplot, Version 14.0).

3. Results

3.1. Acoustic reference measurements

Fig. 3A shows the displacement magnitude of the stapes for all TBs ($N=14$) for analysis in reference to the ear canal SPL (METF) compared to the ASTM standard (ASTM, 2005). Fig. 3B shows the intracochlear pressure differences magnitudes of all TBs relative to the SPLs in the ear canal. The trend is similar to the data presented by Nakajima et al. (2009) with the resonance peak at approximately 1 kHz. TB03-TB12 ($N=8$) were used for experiment 1 (FMT stimulation) while TB17-TB27 ($N=6$) were used for piezoelectric stimulation.

Fig. 3. (A) The stapes displacement response in all temporal bones ($N=14$) employed in this study relative to the sound pressure level at the TM, compared to the reference data (ASTM, 2005; Koch et al., 2022). (B) Intracochlear pressure differences in response to the acoustic stimuli in the ear canal compared to the Nakajima et al., 2009 (shaded area). TB03-TB12 ($N=8$) were subsequently used for FMT stimulation (experiment 1) while TB17-TB27 ($N=6$) were used for stimulation with the piezoelectric actuator (experiment 2).

3.2. Experiment 1 – FMT stimulation

Fig. 4A shows the equivalent SPLs, as calculated from the intracochlear pressure differences, of the FMT driven with 100 mV_p input and attached to the three different OWC versions. Using only the OWC-S attached to the FMT for the stimulation, almost no pressure signal with sufficient SNR was recorded. At mid-frequencies, we could measure the intracochlear pressures in both scalae with sufficient SNR, but only with high variability. The average pressure difference was up to 10 dB between the medium and the large shoe. The difference between the output (eq. dB SPL) of the FMT attached to the medium (OWC-M) and the large adapter (OWC-L) was significant (t-test; $p=0.02$) only in mid-frequency band ($1 \text{ kHz} \leq f \leq 4 \text{ kHz}$). The pair-wise statistical comparison between all other conditions detected no statistical significant differences possibly due to the lack of data at other frequency bands. The corresponding OWC displacement (Fig. 4B) measured by LDV at the opening of the OW showed that the use of adapters decreased the displacements of OWC at low frequencies on average up to 17 dB.

3.3. Experiment 2 - piezoelectric actuator stimulation

The intracochlear pressure difference ($\overrightarrow{P_{\text{Diff}}} = \overrightarrow{P_{SV}} - \overrightarrow{P_{ST}}$) magnitude using the piezoelectric actuator attached to the three different OWC version is illustrated in Fig. 5A. The average pressure differences across all measured frequencies were found to be 18 dB higher for OWC-L and 8 dB higher for the OWC-M compared to OWC-S, respectively. Fig. 5B shows the stimulus provided by the actuator in eq. SPLs (equivalent output of the actuator) at the tympanic membrane normalized to a piston displacement input of 1 μm measured on the OWC. The average equivalent SPLs across all measured frequencies was found to be 20 dB higher for OWC-L and 7 dB higher for the OWC-M compared to OWC-S, respectively. For further statistical analysis, frequencies were divided into three bands ($f < 1 \text{ kHz}$, $1 \text{ kHz} \leq f \leq 4 \text{ kHz}$, $f > 4 \text{ kHz}$). Up to 1 kHz, the output of the actuator at 1 μm displacement had a flat response with an average equivalent output of 75, 84 and 97 dB SPL for the OWC-S, OWC-M and OWC-L, respectively. At frequencies between 1 and 4 kHz, the average output of the OWC-S was lowest with 96 dB SPL compared to 101 and 113 dB SPL for the OWC-M and OWC-L. At frequencies between the 4 and 10 kHz, the average output at 1 μm piston displacement were 124, 129 and 138 dB SPL for the OWC-S, OWC-M and OWC-L, respectively. The differences between stimulation with different piston area conditions were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$; Table 1; Fig. 6) at nearly all frequency bands. Only the difference between the OWC-M and OWC-S in the high frequency band was found to be non-significant ($p = 0.99$; Table 1).

Fig. 4. Output comparison of the FMT stimulation with different piston sizes after stapedectomy. (A) Equivalent sound pressure levels (eq. SPLs) at 100 mV_p input voltage derived from ICPD. The thick solid lines illustrate average magnitudes for the FMT attached to OWC-M (red) and OWC-L (blue), respectively. The shaded areas depict the standard deviations in individual TBs with corresponding colors. Standard deviations are only shown where at least three data points/freq. with sufficient SNR were available, for mean values with < 3 data points/freq. standard deviation ranges are omitted. (B) Piston displacement of the OWCs attached to the FMT measured by the LDV.

Fig. 5. Output comparison of different piston sizes with the piezoelectric actuator stimulation after stapedectomy. Comparison of average magnitude of (A) the intracochlear pressure difference in response to the piezoelectric actuator stimulation at a constant input voltage of 100 mV_p and (B) eq. SPLs normalized to 1 μm displacement of the OWC. The solid lines illustrate average magnitude of the piezo attached to OWC-S (green, N = 6), with OWC-M (red, N = 6) and OWC-L (blue, N = 6). Shaded areas of corresponding color represent the standard deviation range.

Table 1

Statistical comparison of the equivalent sound pressure levels (eq. SPLs) normalized to displacement of the OWC [dB μm] obtained with the OWC-S, OWC-M and OWC-L adapters. A repeated measure of ANOVA was performed (p < 0.05).

Comparison	Freq. band	Mean value ± Standard deviation [eq. dB SPL]	p-value
OWC-L Vs. OWC-S	f < 1.0 kHz	97 ± 6 (N*=60) vs. 75 ± 10 (N=29)	<0.001
OWC-L Vs. OWC-M	f < 1.0 kHz	97 ± 6 (N=60) vs. 84 ± 8 (N=45)	0.038
OWC-M Vs. OWC-S	f < 1.0 kHz	84 ± 8 (N=45) vs. 76 ± 10 (N=29)	0.003
OWC-L Vs. OWC-S	1.0 ≤ f ≤ 4.0 kHz	113 ± 16 (N=48) vs 96 ± 16 (N=44)	<0.001
OWC-L Vs. OWC-M	1.0 ≤ f ≤ 4.0 kHz	113 ± 16 (N=48) vs. 101 ± 20 (N=46)	0.046
OWC-M Vs. OWC-S	1.0 ≤ f ≤ 4.0 kHz	101 ± 20 (N=46) vs. 96 ± 16 (N=44)	0.019
OWC-L Vs. OWC-S	f > 4.0 kHz	138 ± 22 (N=19) vs. 123 ± 12 (N=19)	0.016
OWC-L Vs. OWC-M	f > 4.0 kHz	138 ± 22 (N=19) vs. 129 ± 17 (N=19)	0.026
OWC-M Vs. OWC-S	f > 4.0 kHz	129 ± 17 (N=19) vs. 123 ± 12 (N=19)	0.986

* N shows number of data points with sufficient SNR in the test.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the equivalent sound pressure levels normalized for 1 μm piston displacement of the piezo actuator for the three different oval window couplers (OWC-S green, OWC-M red and OWC-L blue). Lower and upper fences of the boxplot represent 25th and 75th percentiles (whiskers are 10th and 90th percentiles). The statistical analysis (repeated measure of ANOVA) was performed on frequency band average results (Table 1); statistical significant differences are indicated by * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01.

3.4. FMT stimulation - lumped element model

As pressures could not be recorded with sufficient SNR for FMT stimulation, the lumped element model was employed to estimate the stimulation output with the three different OWC versions in a numerical

model. The results of this simulation are depicted in Fig. 7 and show that the OWC-L generates an output up to 8 dB higher than the OWC-S, while the OWC-M produces an output up to 7 dB higher than the OWC-S across frequencies ranging from 0.3 to 10 kHz. The differences at lower frequencies (<300 Hz) were significantly smaller with nearly identical output predictions for all OWC versions. The difference between output using OWC-M and OWC-L below 1 kHz was minor.

The model predicts qualitatively the output of the FMT attached to the OWC when stimulating the intact SFP at mid frequencies (> 1 kHz, black dotted line) without an open gap (Huttenbrink et al., 2008). In contrast, for small open gaps with the OWC-L, the model predicts an approximately 10 dB higher output at frequencies below 1 kHz and approximately 20 dB higher for frequencies below 7 kHz (Fig. 7). This difference was even more pronounced for the OWC-M and possibly much higher for the large open gap condition with the OWC-S that was barely measurable due to low SNR. Also, the output differences between OWC sizes (M/L) found experimentally were higher than expected by the model prediction, especially in the mid-frequency range between 0.5–3 kHz (Fig. 4).

4. Discussion

The present study investigated whether the effective area of the employed piston affects OW stimulation efficiency with an AMEI. In contrast to actuator stimulation investigated here, stapesplasty in patients uses the tympanic membrane or residues of the ossicles to drive a piston prosthesis inserted into the perilymph. However, results are controversial as some clinical studies (Laske et al., 2011; Blijleven et al., 2024) and model evaluations (Rosowski and Merchant, 1995) showed an increase in stimulation efficacy for increasing piston diameters while other clinical investigations did not find any significant interrelations (Hornung et al., 2011; Cavaliere et al., 2012; Fucci et al., 1998). In surgical reconstruction of the middle ear with a passive piston prosthesis, the mechanical transmission properties of the ossicular chain are not independent of the condition at the output. Changing the boundary conditions at the output e.g. by a piston affects the entire system from the tympanic membrane to the OW and changes in transmission properties partially compensate each other. In contrast thereto, the output of a mechanical actuator is mainly independent of the load, type of coupler and employed piston diameter and stimulation efficiency is mainly determined by the interface to the cochlea. Unfortunately, the outcomes of clinical investigations are not sufficient to derive reliable conclusions for actuated piston stimulation:

Due to these limitations, the present experimental study was

Fig. 7. Comparison of model's output with the average equivalent sound pressure levels (eq. SPLs) of the three OWC version using the FMT at 100 mV_p input. The dash-dotted black line shows an earlier experiment of the FMT with OWC on the stapes footplate sealed by an intact annular ligament. The thin solid line illustrates the average magnitude of the FMT output with OWC-L in our experiments (Fig. 4) for comparison, whereas the dashed lines show the predicted output of the model without an open gap.

conducted to derive if the size of the stimulating piston matters if directly stimulating the cochlear perilymph through the OW with an AMEI. Two different actuators—the FMT of the Vibrant Soundbridge and a piezoelectric transducer—were coupled to piston OW couplers with three different cross sectional areas and employed to stimulate the perilymph in human cadaver temporal bones after SFP removal. The measured intracochlear pressure differences consistently demonstrated that a larger stimulation area enhances efficiency:

The average output of the FMT, expressed as eq. SPL, was approximately 10 dB higher in mid-frequency range (1–4 kHz; $p < 0.05$; t-test) when using the large piston size (OWC-L) compared to the medium size (OWC-M). Intracochlear pressures were barely recordable with sufficient SNR for the smallest piston size OWC-S, also indicating that the smaller surface area provides lower output. No definitive conclusions could be drawn regarding FMT stimulation at low and high frequencies, primarily due to insufficient SNR resulting from the limited output of the FMT in these frequency ranges.

In order to overcome this limitation, a piezo actuator was employed instead of the FMT in a second series of experiments. The corresponding experimental results showed that at frequencies up to 1 kHz, the average output increased by 22 dB when using the largest piston ($A_{\text{OWC-L}}=3.06 \text{ mm}^2$) compared to the smallest one ($A_{\text{OWC-S}}=0.38 \text{ mm}^2$), which is comparable to the ratio of the corresponding surface areas ($A_{\text{OWC-L}} / A_{\text{OWC-S}}=18 \text{ dB}$). The difference at higher frequency-bands became smaller with increasing frequency (13 dB (1.0–4.0 kHz) and 6 dB (4.0–8.0 kHz)), but remained statistically significant (cf. Table 1; Fig. 6). These findings are consistent with an earlier clinical study by Busch et al. who investigated AMEI stimulation with a different device in patients. They showed that stimulation through the OW, i.e., with an effective surface area of 0.13 mm^2 (diameter 0.4 mm), provides 28 to 36 dB less output compared to stimulation by the SFP with an average area of 3.2 mm^2 . This reduction was also nearly identical to the ratio difference between the two surface areas (Busch et al., 2021).

Furthermore, a numerical model of the FMT attached to the inner ear was developed. The goal was to simulate the output of the FMT with the three piston surface sizes, especially at frequencies where intracochlear pressures could not be sufficiently measured experimentally, and to further understand the origin of differences in stimulation efficacy. The model predicted that the medium (OWC-M) and large (OWC-L) pistons generate comparable output across the entire frequency range. Simulations also demonstrated up to 8 dB higher stimulation output of the two larger pistons compared to the smaller one (OWC-S) for frequencies above 300 Hz, further supporting the claim that larger piston sizes increase stimulation efficacy.

Our model-predicted results (Fig. 7) show that increasing the OWC diameter enhances the FMT's OW stimulation efficiency, particularly at high frequencies. This improvement is due to the increased cochlear input volume velocity, which aligns with the lumped element model analysis for passive total ossicular replacement prosthesis (TORP) by Rosowski et al. (Rosowski and Merchant, 1995). Comparison of our model-predicted results with experimental data from Huttenbrink et al. (2008) with an FMT + OWC to stimulate the intact mobile SFP indicate that our model predictions are close to the experimental data at frequencies above 1 kHz, as shown in Fig. 7.

However, the model-predicted eq. SPLs at mid-frequencies (<7 kHz) are > 20 dB higher than our experimental results. This discrepancy is probably due to the open gap around the piston prosthesis in the stapedectomy in our experiments, that is omitted in our and many other models. This acoustic short-circuit and associated pressure loss i.e., a partial volume balancing at the OW if the OW is not sealed around the stimulating piston, by a liquid-air interface in experiments or liquid-tissue interface in patients is not accounted for in our simulation. Although acoustic properties of water and tissue are similar, the open-gap effect may be different clinically. As it can be assumed that the open gap area in a stapedectomy is likely to be overgrown by tissue the resulting condition may not correspond to the experimental situation

investigated in this study. At higher frequencies (>7 kHz), the model-predicted results are closer to the experimental data, likely due to the increasing influence of cochlear fluid inertia. Nevertheless, our results demonstrate that the open-gap effect has major impact on stimulation efficiency besides the piston size.

The effect of the open gap was also noted by Burovikhin et al. (Burovikhin and Lauxmann, 2025) in their finite element analysis. They found that an open gap between a partial ossicular replacement prosthesis piston and the opening of the SFP after stapedotomy reduced the RW volume velocity by more than 10 dB at lower frequencies (<1 kHz) and more than 7 dB at mid-high frequencies (>1 kHz). In our case, the open gap between the OWC and oval window in a stapedectomy was larger than the one studied by Burovikhin et al., especially for the OWC-S. Thus, the OWC-S's eq. SPL can be expected to be significantly lower than the model-predicted result, especially at lower frequencies. This might have contributed to the inability to measure the evoked intracochlear pressures for the FMT+OWC-S. Under the assumption of a 3.2 mm² SFP area, the open gap for the OWC-L is approximately 0.14 mm², much smaller than the open gap in the OWC-M (around 1.94 mm²). Therefore, the impact of the open gap on the OWC-M was larger than on the OWC-L, which could explain why the difference between the OWC-M and OWC-L was greater than our model predicted results.

Finally, our model shows that the differences in eq. SPLs across different OWCs are only slightly affected by the changes in OWC mass (data not shown). This is because the mass of the OWC is much smaller than that of the ossicular chain and FMT (see supplementary table 1). This finding is also consistent with the results reported by Rosowski and Merchant (1995) and Burovikhin and Lauxmann (2025).

In summary, we could demonstrate experimentally with custom made coupler designs that stimulation efficiency increases with larger piston size. Further, the numerical model illustrates, beside the beneficial effect of the increased piston cross-section, that the leakage at the unsealed open gap is detrimental for output.

5. Conclusion

The present experimental investigation demonstrates that oval window stimulation with an active middle ear implant driven piston is significantly increased by an increased piston diameter. For the purpose of our experiments an accessory was designed that increases the effective area of the oval window coupler when stimulating the perilymph directly through the oval window. Using a piston of $A = 3.06 \text{ mm}^2$, approximately the size of the oval window, generates an equivalent sound pressure level of 95–100 eq. dB SPL at 1 μm displacement at low frequencies below 1 kHz and increases at higher frequencies. Additionally, the numerical simulation indicates that volume leakage at open gaps in the oval window reduces stimulation efficiency and has to be considered for future models.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohammad Ghoncheh: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniel Schurzig:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **David Stauske:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Thomas Lenarz:** Writing – review & editing. **Nils Prenzler:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Houguang Liu:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Hannes Maier:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Conflict of interest

D. Schurzig and D. Stauske are employees of MEDEL. M. Ghoncheh and H. Maier received travel support by MEDEL to conferences. The authors disclose no other conflicts of interest.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.heares.2025.109411](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2025.109411).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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